

Reducing CO₂ emissions to zero within the power sector by 2050... Can CLEWs provide a solution?

Amrita Raghoebarsing & Devika Jhagroe
Anton de Kom University of Suriname
Suriname

13 February 2025

Keywords: CLEWs, energy modelling, Suriname, CO₂ emissions

Acknowledgements

This report was produced during the EMP-LAC 25 capacity building event organized by the Climate Compatible Growth Programme (CCG). CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. The CLEWs training was provided by Taco Niet and Osmar Cuadra. The event received funding from CCG, the World Bank Group (WBG), and the 2050 Pathways Platform. We like to thank Climate Compatible Growth, International Centre for Theoretical Physics, World Bank Group, 2050 Pathways Platform, Universidad de la Matanza and the British Embassy of Buenos Aires as the organizers of the EMP-LAC 25.

Executive Summary

Suriname has set no overall total annual emission reduction targets. For this study, two scenarios have been explored whereby the business-as-usual scenario and the second scenario of achieving zero CO₂ emissions by the power sector by 2050. The target to achieve zero CO₂ emissions by the power sector by 2050 can be achieved by limiting the CO₂ emissions of the power sector annually by 4%. Hereby, Hydro and Offshore Wind power plants will be the major technologies to contribute to reaching this target. HFO and NGS power plants must be gradually replaced by Hydro and Offshore Wind until 2050. As a result of this, there will be a decrease in the water demand (~ 0.15 Billion m³) by the power sector. For future work, an elaborate study can be done for Suriname to have a better insight into the energy-, water-, and land systems and the interlinkages of these systems. CLEWs can be very beneficial for Suriname for policymakers, different organizations and the industry sector for creating policies and targets related to energy, water and land and their effects on the other systems.

1. Introduction

To provide insightful consideration for the availability of energy, land and water simultaneously, CLEWs (Climate, land-use, energy and water systems) models prove to be a valuable tool. The tool can be used to analyse how resource systems are affected by changes in climate, to optimize the production and use of these resources. The model can incorporate different technologies and implicate stressors, to reach synergies and trade-offs to meet development goals.

Suriname has set no overall total annual emission reduction targets. However, for the high carbon emission sectors specific targets and measures are in place, as well as clear adaptation goals in the NAP (National Adaptation Plan) with an emphasis on nature-

based solutions (to protect the high forest cover). The country's NDC (Nationally Determined Contributions) includes several sustainable development goals highlighting the national priorities.

The annual electricity demand in Suriname grows by approximately 5%. As of now, electricity is provided by hydropower and solar PV (renewables) for around 30%, while fossil fuels (HFO and Diesel) generate around 70%.

The question that needs to be addressed is: can CLEWs provide a good solution for reducing CO₂ emissions to zero within the power sector by 2050?

A map of Suriname is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Map of Suriname

2. Methodology

The CLEWs model in the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) interface is used for Suriname in order to optimize the energy generation while limiting CO₂ emissions by the power sector to zero. The modelling has been done from 2020 to 2050. To set up the energy profile for Suriname, the generic Starter data kit (SDK on the CCG online platform) has been used as there was no specific data available for Suriname. In figure 2 the simplified system reference diagram of Suriname is presented.

Figure 2 Simplified system reference diagram of Suriname using CLEWs

Data sources:

- Energy sector data were obtained from SDK from the CCG website
- For the Land system, data were obtained from the website of FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization) and OECD (Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development)
- For the water system, data were obtained from the website of FAO (aquastat)
- General country data were obtained from the website of IEA (International Energy Agency)

Two scenarios have been worked out for this study namely:

1: Business as usual scenario (BAU): two new power production technologies in the already existing matrix were added from 2026 onwards: natural gas and offshore wind power plants. No further restrictions were set with regards to the power capacity of these power plants.

For the land systems, top four cultivated crops that were taken into account namely (rainfed and irrigated) rice, banana, sugarcane and palm oil.

For the water system, the following end users were taken into consideration: agriculture, public supply and power sector

2: Reduction of CO₂ emissions to zero within the power sector by 2050, while:

a) The annual CO₂ emission limit was set to decrease annually by 4% by 2050;

b) The CO₂ emissions by diesel within the Agriculture sector remained unchanged.

3. Results

Results of Scenario 1 BAU and Scenario 2 for Power Generation

For the BAU scenario, two new technologies (natural gas and offshore wind power plants) were added for power generation in the future. As shown in the figure 4, for the BAU case, HFO will be replaced after 2026. After 2030 the generation will be done with hydro, NGS, solar PV and offshore wind.

In order to achieve zero CO₂ emissions by 2050, it can be seen (graph of scenario 2) that a decrease in the power generation with NGS, Solar PV, Hydro must happen after 2026 while a significant increase with offshore wind power plants. The power generation by HFO can completely be phased out. Nearly 85% of the generation needs to be done with offshore wind power plants and 15% with hydro to achieve zero CO₂ emissions by 2050.

Scenario 1: Business-as-usual (BAU)

Scenario 2: Reduction of CO₂

Figure 3 Power Generation

Results of Scenario 1 BAU and Scenario 2 for CO₂ Emissions

Due to the NGS power plants which will be installed in 2026, the CO₂ emissions will be annually 0.30 Mton or more in the BAU. However, for scenario 2 the CO₂ emission will annually decrease from 2026 until 2050 till it reaches zero in 2050.

Scenario 1: Business-as-usual (BAU)

Scenario 2: Reduction of CO₂

Figure 4 CO₂ Emission by Sector

Results of Scenario 1 BAU and Scenario 2 for Water Demand

The highest demand of water in Suriname is by the power sector and this goes for both the cases. In scenario 2 however, a significant decrease (~ 0.15 Billion m³) in demand is observed and the value keeps dropping till 2050.

Scenario 1: Business-as-usual (BAU)

Scenario 2: Reduction of CO₂

Figure 5 Water Demand

4. Discussion

As the power sector in Suriname is one of the most CO₂-intensive industries, the Government needs to have CO₂ emission targets and Renewable energy targets to limit the emissions within this sector. With the results of this study, we can have an insight

into how to reach zero CO₂ emission within this sector. If the CO₂ target is set to decrease annually by 4% by 2050 and the HFO power plants will not be used anymore then we can reach zero emissions by 2050. NGS power plants have not been implemented yet (2025), so if no NGS power plants are implemented by 2050, the target can be reached.

A potential technology that can be explored in Suriname within the power sector is the implementation of wind power.

More areas can be explored within the CLEWs model but due to lack of time, it was not possible to do an elaborate study e.g. no land was allocated to the various power plants. If land area was allocated to the various power plants then it would be possible to see the effect of the implementation of power plants on land cover and also on forest cover. For future work, an elaborate study can be done for Suriname to have a better insight into the energy-, water-, and land systems and the interlinkages of these systems. CLEWs can be very beneficial for Suriname for policymakers, different organisations and the industry sector for creating policies and targets related to energy, water and land and their effects on the other systems. One of the main challenges for implementing a better CLEWs model will be to have accurate data of Suriname on these 3 systems.

5. Conclusion

The target to achieve zero CO₂ emissions by the power sector by 2050 can be achieved by limiting the CO₂ emissions of the power sector annually by 4%. Hereby, Hydro and Offshore Wind power plants will be the major technologies to contribute to reaching this target. HFO and NGS power plants must be gradually replaced by Hydro and Offshore Wind until 2050. As a result of this, there will be a decrease in the water demand (~ 0.15 Billion m³) by the power sector.

For this study, specific and accurate data of Suriname is required and more detailed modelling must be done to have a better and more accurate model for Suriname. This will lead to more accurate results and will be better for creating policies and targets for the country.

References

1. <https://wwf.panda.org/discover/our-focus/climate-and-energy-practice/ndcs/reviewed-ndcs/suriname/>
2. Government of the Republic of Suriname (2023). Third National Communication of the Republic Suriname to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
3. N.V. EBS Electricity Company Suriname. Masterplan.

*The views expressed in this material do not necessarily reflect the UK Government

